

PORTUGUESE COLONIES IN ANGOLA AND MOZAMBIQUE HAD DISTINCT CHARACTERISTICS IN THE FORMATION OF THEIR LABOR SYSTEMS.

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Abstract: This article examines the specific features of the formation of the working class in the social life of Angola and Mozambique, which were under the rule of Portugal during the colonial period. Migration processes of the local population to many countries have been revealed after gaining independence.

Key words: Retornados, Bantu, Malawi, prazos, colonies, Carnation Revolution, empire.

During the early years of the XX century, labor force was recruited from Northern Rhodesia, Mozambique, and New Zealand to work in the gold mines in Southern Rhodesia, attracting hundreds of thousands of workers. The Portuguese government, through a series of conventions with the government of South Africa, controlled the labor force from Mozambique to the gold mines. Taxes levied on migrants were the main source of state revenue. Deferred payments ensured the return of migrants, tax payments, and enabled the purchase of Portuguese manufactured goods. Mozambique Transvaal obtained the concession for railway transportation. Similarly, in Angola, based on the San-Tome agreement, it was sent to work. After allegations of slavery emerged in 1908, this system was discontinued. San-Tome workers also had to appeal to Mozambique for work. The majority of Mozambican labor migrants came from the region south of the Save River. Portuguese, from the north, granted significant privileges in the 1890s to charter companies for railway, agriculture, and trade. According to the old "prazos" system, charter companies controlled more than half of the colony's land. Just like in other parts of the colony, such as Angola, Africans also had to produce specified quotas of cotton and rubber. Despite numerous laws to protect them, there were frequent abuses.

By 1945, more than 4/5 of Portugal's cotton came directly from Mozambique and Angola. Expanding the empire's territories at the expense of indigenous peoples was unjust. Portugal, being one of the first European states to expand its borders, embarked on a global colonization effort. In the 15th century, the colonization of South America began. However, during the same period, Portugal established trading posts in Africa, such as Angola and Mozambique. Over three centuries, Portugal profited greatly from the vast

amounts of gold and precious stones obtained from its colonies in South America. But by the 19th century, most of these colonies were no longer under Portuguese control. Former Portuguese colonies had gained independence by this time. With only one place left to expand, Portugal fiercely competed for African territories. When Portugal turned its attention to Africa, it outperformed other European nations. Portugal managed numerous trading posts across the continent. Cape Verde, Guinea-Bissau, São Tomé and Príncipe were the first places Portugal colonized in Africa. Portugal, like Spain, had been managing major trading posts in Angola and Mozambique on the western coast of Africa. Both were Portuguese colonies in Africa. However, Portugal expanded its regulations. It developed a plan to control the territories between Angola and Mozambique. This later aimed to secure territories such as Malawi (formerly Nyasaland), Zambia (formerly Northern Rhodesia), and Zimbabwe (formerly Southern Rhodesia) under its control. This plan required Portugal to exert strong influence in Africa. There was a state that opposed Portugal's regulations, which was the British Empire. At the time when Portugal wanted to expand across the continent, Britain had started to expand from north to south and from south to north. Great Britain granted significant privileges to individuals such as Cecil Rhodes for the railway line project. However, from Kohira to Keyptaung, they fell under imperial control. Portugal was not capable of competing with Britain for territories in Africa. Indeed, these two states had been allies for a long time, so Portugal was forced to stop its own regulations and cede its territories in Angola and Mozambique to Britain. When it comes to governing colonies, Portugal leaned not towards state-supported imperialism but rather towards a model similar to Britain's. The expansion and daily activities of the colonies were left to private companies. Among these private companies were the Niassa, Zambezi, and Mozambique companies. Many Portuguese settlers intermarried with local Africans, resulting in the emergence of a mixed-race population (referred to later as mulatto or more broadly as mestizo).

In the 19th century, Angola was declared an official province of Portugal. However, in the early 20th century, the colonial government allowed a large-scale influx of white settlers into Angola and its other provinces. By 1960, there were up to 172,000 Portuguese settlers in Angola, who had contributed significantly to its economy. Most of them had come from Portugal's agricultural sector. They viewed engagement in trade in Angola as one of the limited social mobility opportunities available to them. In 1961, the Angolan War of Independence began, leading to the accelerated development of Angola's

national consciousness. Portuguese military personnel, as well as civil servants and other individuals, were deployed. As a result, the number of Portuguese residents in Angola approached 350,000. If they hadn't emigrated to other countries, especially Namibia, Brazil, South Africa, and the United States, this number would have been much higher. At that time, the majority of Portuguese residents in Angola were supportive of Portugal's efforts to suppress the independence movement. Among them was the Angolan writer Pepetela. When the Salazar regime in Portugal ended in 1974 following a military coup, independence was granted to the colonies by the new government. After gaining independence in 1975, many white Angolans chose to leave. The "Retornados" were not always warmly welcomed and some migrated to Namibia (then South West Africa), South Africa, Brazil, or the USA. According to estimates, nearly 250,000 people left the country in 1975. By 1976, only around 30-40 thousand remained in Angola. Upon arrival in Portugal, those who brought their savings from Angola could not exchange more than 5,000 Angolan escudos (approximately 200 US dollars) into Portuguese escudos.

They were given a few months to choose Angolan citizenship or to leave the country. The majority opted for Angolan citizenship, and some of them had actively participated in the Angolan Civil War, usually on the side of the MPLA. After the socialist regime that ruled Angola until 1975 fell following independence, many Portuguese Angolans returned to Angola. Due to Angola's economic growth starting in the 1990s, the number of Portuguese who hadn't previously been connected to Angola economically, most notably, due to economic reasons, relocated, especially in the recent national economic boom. Portugal's last colony, under the dictatorship of Salazar in Portugal, endured the lesser-known Colonial War from 1961 to 1974, which ended in 1974. The Colonial War aimed to maintain sufficient strength to resist independence aspirations for Portugal's colonies in Africa, while holding onto remaining territories abroad. In Portugal, Salazar was succeeded by Caetano. Later in 1974, the democratic government sought to swiftly end the Colonial War. To achieve this, Portugal needed to negotiate with representatives from each colony. Hence, the "Carnation Revolution" occurred, leading to Portugal's withdrawal from Africa. After Angola gained independence on November 11, 1975, Portugal's last colony in Africa was left to fend for itself. The departure of Portuguese administration left a power vacuum, leading to the rise of leftist governments, especially in former colonies like Angola and Mozambique. The Soviet Union and the communist government of Cuba began to support communist governments

and insurgents. At the same time, Antonio de Oliveira Salazar was leading Portugal, during which several thousand Portuguese fled to other countries, especially to Rhodesia and South Africa, Brazil, and the United States. Black Angolans, some mulattos, and whites rose in rebellion against Portuguese rule in 1974. The United States, South Africa, and other states supported the opposition. Civil war broke out in both countries. The Angolan Civil War was one of the longest and bloodiest conflicts in Africa, lasting 27 years. This war resulted in the displacement of 500,000 civilians. Former Portuguese colonies have made several improvements in recent years in terms of stability and development. After leaving Portugal, they have retained only the Azores, Madeira, and the Savage Islands as Portugal's overseas territories. Their mother tongue remains Portuguese, and today, Angolan Portuguese is considered the official language and lingua franca. Until the early 20th century, communities living in Luanda, Benguela, and Mocamedes spoke African languages mixed with elements of Portuguese, especially Kimbundu and Umbundu. However, due to the influx of new settlers from Portugal in the 20th century, their language has become almost identical to European Portuguese, largely due to the influence of colonization.

Some Portuguese Angolans have a good command of Bantu languages, especially Kimbundu, Umbundu, and Kikongo. However, their numbers have sharply declined since independence, and hardly anyone uses an African language as a second language anymore. Many well-educated Portuguese Angolans during the colonial period learned French and, to a lesser extent, English. Since independence, both white and black Angolans have been learning English, while French has taken a back seat. The majority of Portuguese Angolans are Catholics, but many do not practice their religion. A significant portion of them are Jewish, with debates about the advantages and disadvantages of their ancestors fleeing the Inquisition.

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